

A Visible-Near Infrared Light Responsive Host-Guest Pair with Nanomolar Affinity in Water

Pedro Ferreira,^[a] Barbara Ventura,^[b] Andrea Barbieri,^[b] José P. Da Silva,^[c] César A. T. Laia,^[a] A. Jorge Parola,^{[a]*} and Nuno Basílio^{[a]*}

Dedication ((optional))

Abstract: The discovery of stimuli-responsive high affinity host-guest pairs with potential applications under biological relevant conditions is a challenging goal. Herein we report a high-affinity 1:1 complex formed between cucurbit[8]uril and a water soluble photochromic diarylethene derivative. We found that confining the open isomer within the cavity of the receptor induces a red-shift in the absorption spectrum and leads to an enhancement of the photocyclization quantum yield from $\Phi = 0.04$ to $\Phi = 0.32$. This improvement in the photochemical performance enables quantitative photocyclization with visible light that together with the near-infrared light induced ring-opening reaction and the 100-fold selectivity for the closed isomer confirms this as an outstanding light-responsive affinity pair.

Supramolecular chemistry provides extraordinary tools to design and realize complex functional materials from molecular building blocks held together by noncovalent bonds.^[1,2] Complementary recognition units with high affinity and selectivity for their binding counterparts are required for efficient and robust self-assembled materials. Natural systems provide remarkable examples of highly complementary pairs such as nitrogenous DNA bases, antibody-antigen and ligand-protein that often serve as inspiration for construction of artificial systems.^[3–8] Cucurbit[n]urils (CBn) are pumpkin-shaped macrocyclic receptors that display very high-affinity and selectivity for complementary guest molecules in aqueous solution. Binding constants up to $\approx 10^{17}$ M⁻¹ have been reported which rival the popular biotin-(strep)avidin high-affinity biological pair ($K \approx 10^{15}$ M⁻¹).^[9–13] CBn can be employed in numerous applications that are based on the extraordinary high affinity displayed by these macrocycles. Examples include recognition, self-assembly and isolation of biomolecules, noncovalent functionalization of biopharmaceuticals, bioimaging and supramolecular materials

such as polymers, microcapsules and supramolecular organic frameworks.^[14–31]

A key feature of supramolecular systems relies on the reversible nature of noncovalent bonds allowing control of association processes using external stimuli. Light is recognized as a superior stimulus for many applications because it allows for remote spatiotemporal control, it is orthogonal to other stimuli and additional reagents are not required.^[32,33] While different host-guest complexes formed from CBn and photoresponsive guests had been reported, most of them show binding affinities in the micromolar range or above.^[34–40] It is worth noting that some anthracene derivatives are known to form highly stable 1:2 photodimerizable host:guest complexes although with poor reversibility.^[41] Herein we report the formation of a photoresponsive host-guest complex between CB8 and a diarylethene derivative, which displays nanomolar affinity in the closed form (**1c**) and 100-fold lower affinity in the open form (**1o**). This differential interaction can be used to photoregulate the complexation of high-affinity guest molecules through competitive binding (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. (a) Structures of molecules investigated in this work. (b) Photocontrolled complexation and release of high-affinity guest molecules from CB8.

Diarylethenes (DAE) have attracted considerable interest owing to their outstanding photochromic properties.^[42] In previously reported CBn:DAE complexes the macrocycle binds to

- [a] Pedro Ferreira, Dr. César A. T. Laia, Dr. A. Jorge Parola, Dr. Nuno Basílio
Laboratório Associado para a Química Verde (LAQV), Rede de Química e Tecnologia (REQUIMTE), Departamento de Química, Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, (Portugal)
E-mail: ajp@fct.unl.pt
E-mail: nuno.basilio@fct.unl.pt
- [b] Dr. Barbara Ventura, Dr. Andrea Barbieri
Istituto per la Sintesi Organica e la Fotoreattività (ISOF)
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)
Via P. Gobetti 101, 40129 Bologna (Italy).
- [c] Dr. José Paulo Da Silva
CCMAR - Centre of Marine Sciences
University of Algarve
Campus de Gambelas, 8005-139 Faro (Portugal)

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peripheral groups decorating the DAE rather than the photoactive unit, precluding significant differences in the stability of the complexes upon switching between the open and closed forms.^[43–45] Preliminary experiments suggested that CB7 binds **1** through the pyridinium units with 2:1 stoichiometry and moderate affinity (above the μM range) for both **1o** and **1c** forms (see Supporting Information, SI, Figures S4–S7). ESI-MS experiments also showed that both **1o** and **1c** form 1:1 complexes with CB8 (see SI, Figure S8) which are supported by UV-Vis titrations (Figure 1). Considerable spectral changes with well-defined isosbestic points can be observed indicating that CB8 forms stable ($K > 1 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1}$) 1:1 host-guest complexes with **1o** and **1c**. Noteworthy, the spectrum of **1o** undergoes a ca. 15 nm bathochromic shift upon complexation allowing photoswitching at more biocompatible wavelengths in the visible range.

Figure 1. Spectral changes observed upon gradual addition of CB8 to a solution of (a) **1o** ($1.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ in H₂O). (b) The same for **1c** ($1.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ in H₂O). In both cases fitting to a 1:1 host:guest model was achieved with $K > 1 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1}$.

Confining photochromic molecules in nanometric cavities may profoundly impact their photochemical properties.^[46–49] As previously observed, **1o** can be converted into **1c** by light irradiation at 365 nm ($\phi = 0.04$) and reverted with wavelengths $> 500 \text{ nm}$ ($\phi = 0.0003$, $\lambda_{\text{irr}} = 550 \text{ nm}$), see SI, Figure S9.^[50] ¹H NMR experiments show that both species are quantitatively interconverted (see SI, Figure S10). Interestingly, encapsulation of **1o** in CB8 leads to a significant acceleration of the photocyclization rate accounting for an increase in the quantum

yield from $\phi = 0.04$ to $\phi = 0.32$ (Figure 2). As already anticipated above, the enhanced photocyclization efficiency of the **1o**:CB8 complex together with its bathochromic shift, allows efficient and quantitative **1o**:CB8 to **1c**:CB8 photoconversion with 435 nm visible light (see SI, Figure S11a).

On the other hand, the quantum yield for inverse ring-opening reaction remains unaffected under confinement ($\phi = 0.0003$ at $\lambda_{\text{irr}} = 550 \text{ nm}$, see SI, Figure S12). Noteworthy, this process can be quantitatively induced by light irradiation in the biological window with NIR wavelengths $\lambda_{\text{irr}} > 715 \text{ nm}$ (see SI, Figure S11b). In addition to photochromic properties, the free open form **1o** displays an unstructured weak fluorescence emission centered at 620 nm ($\phi = 0.37 \times 10^{-2}$, see SI, Figure S13) in de-aerated water solution at room temperature. Upon encapsulation, the intensity increases almost 3-times ($\phi = 1.05 \times 10^{-2}$) and a blue shift from 620 to 590 nm is observed. On the other hand, no emission has been detected from the closed form **1c** either alone or with CB8 (see SI, Table S1).

Figure 2. (a) Spectral variations observed upon irradiation (365 nm) of **1o** in the presence of 1 equiv. of CB8 ($2.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ in H₂O). (b) Normalized absorbance at a single wavelength plotted against the irradiation time in the presence of 1 equiv. of CB8 (688 nm, circles) and in the absence of CB8 (668 nm, squares).

¹H NMR experiments were conducted to investigate the structure of the complexes which, in turn, can provide insight on the improved photocyclization efficiency of confined **1o**. The experiments (Figure 3) showed that for both **1o** and **1c** the signals of protons *d*, *e*, *f* and *g* are displaced to higher field upon CB8 inclusion while protons *c* are displaced downfield, clearly suggesting that the photochromic central moiety of the DAE unit is deeply enclosed in the hydrophobic cavity of CB8 while the pyridinium units remain outside the cavity. The spectra of Figure 3 were initially carried out at room temperature but after noticing that the signal corresponding to the four *e* protons appears substantially broadened, the temperature was decreased to 5 °C. This signal, that shows up as a triplet in the free guest due the high conformational flexibility of **1o**, splits into two broad signals after inclusion suggesting that confinement “freezes” the parallel/antiparallel conformational interconversion. This observation together with the 8-fold increase in the photocyclization quantum yield indicates that the photochemically active antiparallel conformer is selectively stabilized in the cavity of CB8. Previous works showed that cyclodextrins may also displace the parallel/antiparallel ratio towards the photochemically active conformers leading to an increase in the quantum yield.^[51] However, the relative

improvements were modest, which can be attributed to the lower binding affinity and poor selectivity of these flexible macrocycles.

Figure 3 – ^1H NMR spectra of **1o/1c** (0.5 mM in D_2O) in the absence and in the presence of CB8 at 5 °C. For **1c** the spectrum of the complex was acquired with 1 equivalent of CB8 while in the case of **1o** 1.2 equivalent of CB8 were added.

Table 1. Binding constants (K)^[a] obtained for guests 1-8 (Scheme 1) toward CB8 in water using dye displacement assays.^[b]

Guest	K / M^{-1}
1o	5.4×10^7
1c	6.2×10^9
2	$(6.2 \times 10^6)^{[c]}$
3	2.7×10^9 (8.2×10^8) ^[d]
4	1.4×10^7
5	1.1×10^{12} (4.3×10^{11}) ^[d]
6	6.9×10^8 (1.9×10^8) ^[e]
7	8.2×10^9 (3.1×10^9) ^[d]
8	6.9×10^9

[a] Errors are estimated to be equal or below 20%. [b] Previously reported K values are given inside parenthesis for comparison purposes. [c] From reference^[52]. Measured in pure water and used as a reference to obtain the binding constant of **1o** with CB8. [d] From reference^[9]. Measured in 50 mM NaCD_3CO_2 -buffered D_2O (pD=4.74). [e] From reference^[53]. Measured in 50 mM NaCD_3CO_2 solution.

The high binding affinities displayed by CB8 towards **1o** and **1c** precludes the determination of the association constants using direct titration methods. In these cases, competition methods can be used for accurate determination of K values. Methyl viologen (**2**) and adamantane-1-ammonium (**3**) were used as competitors in displacement assays (see SI for details) for the reliable determination of $K_{1o} = 5.4 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1}$ and $K_{1c} = 6.2 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for the complexation of **1o** and **1c** with CB8, respectively. Once established, the high K_{1c} value enables **1c** as a superior optical

probe to investigate the binding of high-affinity guest molecules with CB8 using dye displacement assays (IDA).^[52] The advantages of **1c** over other dyes^[52,54,55] include lack of aggregation, water solubility, 1:1 binding stoichiometry, nanomolar affinity and absorption at low energy wavelengths which enables the study of non-transparent guest molecules such as ferrocene derivatives. The binding constants of guests **4-8** were determined following the IDA approach (see SI, Figure S3) to demonstrate that it can be extended to a wide variety of molecules (Table 1). As can be observed, the K values follow the same trend but are slightly higher than previously reported for guests **3, 5-7**. This can be ascribed to the presence of sodium salts in these studies that are known to reduce the value of K due to cation binding to the CB's portals.^[52]

The two orders of magnitude difference observed for the binding constants of **1o** ($K_{1o} = 5.4 \times 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1}$) and **1c** ($K_{1c} = 6.2 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1}$) towards CB8 provides the required conditions to devise switchable host-guest complexes at nanomolar concentrations. Speciation plots (see SI, Figure S14) show that the mole fraction of complex can be switched from 12% to 80% upon photoconversion of **1o** to **1c** at 3 nM equimolar concentrations or from 10% to 92% for 0.2 nM of dye with 10-fold excess of CB8.

Figure 4. ^1H NMR spectra of (a) **3:CB8** complex (0.5 mM); (b) a ternary mixture containing 0.2 mM CB8, 0.2 mM **3** and 0.5 mM **1o**; (c) the same as in (b) after irradiation and (d) **3** (0.5 mM). All spectra were acquired in D_2O at 5 °C to improve the resolution of exchangeable signals of **3**. Filled circles correspond to singlet signal of CB8 complexed with **3** and open circles complexed with **1o** or **1c**. Filled squares correspond to signals of **3** complexed with CB8 and open squares correspond to free **3**.

At higher concentrations the photoresponsive binding of **1o** into **1c** can be used to regulate the complexation of high affinity guests such as **3** through competitive binding (see Scheme 1). The release of **3** from the CB8 cavity can be demonstrated by ^1H NMR experiments (Figure 4; see also SI, Figure S15 for comparative spectra of all species). Figures 4a and 4d show the spectra of free and complexed **3**, respectively. The key experiments are shown in Figures 4b and 4c: the ^1H NMR spectrum (Fig. 4b) of 0.2 mM CB8, 0.2 mM **3** and 0.5 mM **1o** (an excess was used to optimize guest release) shows that the DAE appears mainly as a free species in solution while very broad signals appear in the highlighted region corresponding to complexed **3** (filled squares), confirming the selective binding of **3**. The highlighted CB8 signals (open and closed circles) that

appear in slow exchange on the chemical shift time scale can be used to quantify the fraction of CB8 complexed with **3** (filled circles, 70%) and with **1o** (open circles, 30%). After quantitative conversion of **1o** into **1c** through light irradiation of the mixture ($\lambda_{\text{irr}} = 365 \text{ nm}$), the appearance of signals corresponding to complexed (and free) **1c** can be clearly observed. On the other hand, the broad signals corresponding to complexed **3** completely vanish (filled squares) while a new set of signals corresponding to free **3** can be readily identified (open squares) demonstrating its photoinduced release. Again, integration of the highlighted CB8 signals shows that after irradiation, the fraction of host complexed with **3** decreases from 70% to 16% corresponding to an effective release of 77%. On the other hand, the mole fraction of 1:CB8 complex increases from 30 to 84%.

In summary, we have shown that the water soluble photochromic diarylethene derivative **1** forms 1:1 host:guest complexes with CB8. Remarkably, the closed isomer **1c** shows nanomolar affinity for the macrocyclic receptor while for the open isomer **1o** the binding constant decreases by two orders of magnitude. This differential binding affinity confers light-responsive properties to the host-guest system allowing remote control over the association/dissociation process in the nanomolar concentration range and photoregulation of the complexation of classic high-affinity pairs through competitive binding. In addition to the enhanced binding affinity, the photoresponsive 1:CB8 system shows other important features such as water solubility, fluorescence emission, quantitative and fully photoreversible interconversion between the closed and open isomers, improved photocyclization efficiency of **1o** to **1c** with visible light upon host inclusion and photoinduced ring opening from **1c** to **1o** using red/near infrared light (in the "biological window") making it a superior photoresponsive binding pair with a strong potential to be explored in future applications based on the host-guest systems.

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